

Leveraging Business Analytics for e-Governance

Kalyani Sahastrabudde¹, Ravindra Bavaskar² and Shikhar Jha³

^{1&2}Assistant Professor and ³Student,

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

CITATION: Sahastrabudde, Kalyani; Bavaskar, Ravindra and Jha, Shikhar (2018), "Leveraging Business Analytics for e-Governance", *MERC Global's International Journal of Management*, Vol. 6, Issue 4, pp. 188-191.

ARTICLE HISTORY: Submitted: June 29, 2018, Revision received: August 07, 2018, Accepted: August 20, 2018

ARTICLE TYPE: Review paper

ABSTRACT

Traditionally, in India, the interaction between the government and the citizens was through an office located far away from the citizen's home, causing inconvenience in terms of waiting time and money lost due to travelling and having to take leave on a working day. With the advent of technology, e-Governance resourcefulness in India and abroad has embarked on a new journey to introduce data analytical tools. These tools are adept at organising and interpreting large amounts of data efficiently at a low cost to analyse e-Governance projects. e-Governance is a host of government agencies that operate online to benefit the citizens in terms of time and money. This will enhance citizens' trust in government agencies as they project more transparency and help them involve the citizens as stakeholders while making government policies. This review has also illustrated the challenges of e-Governance varies between different countries, especially in the urban and rural sectors. Nevertheless, the advent of technology like Big Data has improved the governments' efficiency and functioning and benefitted its citizens by improving their quality of life.

KEYWORDS: Business Analytics; e-Governance, Big Data.

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditionally in India, the interaction between the government and the citizens was through an office located far away from the citizen's home, causing inconvenience in terms of waiting time and money lost due to travelling and having to take leave on a working day. The advent of technology has simplified the procedure for both parties, and e-Governance is now the computerisation of paper-based processes.

This will give rise to new methods of conveying information- listening to the communities and citizens about their issues; leadership; evaluation and decision on strategies, etc. it will also help to strengthen the government's stance on better governance, enhanced transparency to manage the country's economic and social resources (Basu, 2004). Leveraging (read- influence) of business analytics in the e-governance sector translates to better functioning efficiency, transparency, populaces well-being, and involvement in economic growth, public affairs, and national security to predict terrorist activities, crime, intimidations to general safety. The inclusion of big data analytics by like-minded countries can share knowledge for the benefit of their citizens by improving their quality of life and increasing confidence in the administration (Rao *et al.*, 2015).

As the online environment has made a niche in citizens' lives, it's easier for the governments to meet them online by making them engage in government portals and providing them with the much-needed services at a lower cost and time. This will enhance the citizen's trust in the government agencies as they project more transparency and help them involve the citizens as stakeholders while making government policies (Chang and Kannan, 2008).

In India, big data analytic techniques like Association Rule learning; Regression trees; Machine Learning; AI algorithms like Deep Neural Learning networks, etc. Big Data analysis tools like Apache Hadoop are used in e-Governance projects (Navdeep *et al.*, 2016).

The use of data analytic tools like data mining to handle large volumes of data to enhance services to the citizens and will help the government make better decisions and dissemination of information (Navdeep *et al.*, 2016). But the issue is that do these services reach the far-flung rural populations of the developing nations? Thus, this review will also look into the basics of business analytics in e-governance among the developed and underdeveloped countries of the world.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 E-Governance in India

In India, the NeGP (National e-governance plan has been framed by the Department of Electronics and Information Technology and the Department of Administrative reforms and Public Grievances. The citizens of India actively use e-taal (Electronic Transaction Aggregation and Analysis layer), which is a government web portal providing statistical transactions to Indians for e-Governance projects (Navdeep *et al.*, 2016).

But NeGP uses individual databases that are non-uniform and less efficient with sharing information with other public sector domains. To have a successful e-governance platform, there is a need to integrate processes, data, technology, and budget (Rajagopalan and Vellaipandian, 2013).

The various e-Governance projects in India are Land record management projects, Local information projects for loans rates, prices of seeds and fertilisers, Agriculture, Disaster Management, Birth and Death certificates, Pan Card, Voter ID card, Aadhar Card, etc. (Navdeep *et al.*, 2016). Aadhar Card (Unique Identification Authority of India-UIDAI) has been India's most prominent Big Data related project covering 100 crore citizens. The Aadhar number is linked with obtaining a bank account, LPG cylinder for domestic purposes, MNREGA, Passport, etc. (Patel *et al.*, 2017). The other schemes initiated by India are- 'Digital India', 'Make In India', 'Skill India', 'Digi locker', 'MyGov', 'e-Sign Framework' 'Bharat Net', etc.

The challenges faced regarding the use of Big Data Analytics in India are privacy, security especially from unauthorised access, shortage of technical data people to handle and implement this information, lack of standards for representation of data and interoperability, lack of relevant software tools, etc. (Navdeep *et al.*, 2016).

Rajagopalan and Vellaipandian (2013) have found that traditional databases in India are not optimised and are designed to accept structured data for statistical purposes only and have no problem-solving features. The other issues are speed, scalability, availability, and lack of high-performance analysis.

Rajagopalan and Vellaipandian (2013) have suggested a Big Data Framework in their study, which is as follows: Resource management can be handled by Resource management and scheduling platform- Mesos and Yarn to enhance resource utilisation of clusters among multiple processing units like Hadoop, Spark, MPI, etc.; Data organisation and management can be done by RDBMS (Regional database management system) & NoSQL database management system which is optimised in scale and speed to process both static and structured datasets; to report data, data visualisation tools and for advanced analytics, predictive analysis, behavioural analysis, fraud, and comparative analysis, risk analysis, etc.

2.2 E-governance in rural areas of South Africa

Twuinomurinzi *et al.*, (2012) has highlighted issues of e-governance in South Africa. Since 1999 South Africa has started with ICT in rural areas using powerful computers and better bandwidths to integrate the population with services and information from the government to improve their quality of life. These services include health, education, social grants, passports and identification documents, etc. But the social context of the communities is not looked into while implementing the ICT as they are ignorant of the various policies that are meant to empower them. Therefore despite the government's efforts, ICT is mostly one way from the government to the people and not visa-versa.

2.3 Governments Initiatives

Chang and Kannan (2008) have reflected on the government's need to collect feedback data on services and methods to distribute content efficiently to all kinds of citizen groups. They have to find ways to increase their coverage and reach out cost-effectively by engaging intermediaries to create applications for customised services to the citizens. The design of the content has to take into the privacy of the citizens and the security considerations of both the government and the citizens.

2.4 Barriers faced by Governments' with the e-governance Initiatives

In the Government office, the younger age group millennia are more used to be interactive on the web, and the older executives see it as a tool for productivity only. Therefore there are reservations of using social networking tools in the government agencies due to national security issues (Chang and Kannan, 2008).

Furthermore, the challenges faced by countries are two-fold: are the countries e-ready?? There have to be pre-conditions like economic data, legal infrastructure, institutional infrastructure, data systems infrastructure, human and technological infrastructure, and leadership and strategic thinking, and the second issue is adopting the best practices to evade catastrophe (Islam, 2003). Sometimes the citizens are not ready for the technological change (Akther *et al.*, 2007), as in Bangladesh.

The only solution is that the citizens should be convinced to use the internet, and the government can also advertise their e-Services on television and radio. Endeavour in communication infrastructure and training staff in developing countries will go a long way in implementing e-Governance services (Basu, 2004).

2.5 E-Governance and Legal Issues

The success of e-governance topics is also dependant on the existing legal framework for their operation, which varies between different countries, for example, the use of digital signatures on electronic documents. This has been legalised in Hong Kong, Malaysia, Singapore, South Korea, Thailand, Philippines, India, etc. In Summary...

- e-Governance assisted by sophisticated IT tools helps to make informed decisions.
- e-Governance will have to make provisions for guaranteeing the privacy and security of the data collected.
- ICT is a crucial tool connecting the government to the social structure of its population in rural areas and it can help the people interact with the government agencies.
- To implement citizens related schemes to empower the population

Australia	AGIMO (Australian Government information and Management Office uses Bigdata whole of government approach to delivering new services and policies ACBPS(Australian Customs and Border Protection Service)- Passenger analysis
US	BDSSG- Big Data Steering Group – data research and development for Federal Government
UK	Department of business innovation and skills has spent 189 pounds on big data research, even for agriculture technologies
Japan	Regulatory Reform
Denmark	No SQL data to- Operate Nationwide Medical Prescription Card Programme
Sweden	Traffic Patterns, Weather Data
Taiwan	Feasibility study on Introducing Cyber Opinion into Government Decision making process using Big Data
Netherlands	Dutch Flood Control
Korea	Smart Nation
France	Programme of investments of the future
Thailand	Criminal Cases and Human Trafficking
Italy	Income Tax assessment
Norway	Health care

(Information adapted from a study done by Rajagopalan and Vellaipandian, 2013)

3. CONCLUSION

This review has illustrated the challenges of e-Governance varies between different countries, especially in the urban and rural sectors. Nevertheless, the advent of technology like Big Data has improved the governments' efficiency and functioning and benefitted its citizens by improving their quality of life.

4. REFERENCES

1. Akther, MS; Onishi, T. and Kidokoro, T. (2007), "E-government in a developing country. Citizen-Centric approach for success", *Int. Electronic Governance*, Vol. 1(1), pp. 38-51.
2. Bacha, Sami (2015), "Financial Governance, Financing and Investment Program", *MERC Global's International Journal of Management*, Vol. 3, Issue 1, pp. 16-26.
3. Basu, S. (2004), "E-Government and Developing Countries: An Overview", *International Review of Law Computers and Technology*, Vol. 18(1), pp. 109-113.
4. Chang, A.M. and Kannan, P.K. (2008), *Leveraging Web 2.0 in Government*. IBM Centre for the Business Government. www.businessofgovernment.org.
5. Islam, R. (2003), *Do more transparent governments govern better?* The World Bank.
6. Kumar, Atul (2018), "HRM 4.0: High on Expectations", *International Journal of Enhanced Research in Educational Development*, Vol. 6, Issue 1, pp. 24-26.
7. Kumar, Atul; Walke, S. G. and Shetiya, Mahavir M. (2018), "Evaluation of ESOPs as a reward management practice in the Indian IT industry", *International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods*, Vol. 6, Issue 7, July, pp. 46-50.
8. Navdeep, P.; Arora, M., and Sharma, N. (2016), "Role of Big Data Analytics in Analyzing e-Governance Projects", *GyanJyoti E-Journal*.
9. Patel, B.; Roy, S.; Bhattacharya, D. and Kim, T. H. (2017), "The necessity of Big Data Analytics for Good e-governance", *International Journal of Grid and Distributed Computing*, Vol. 10(8), pp. 11-20.
10. Rajagopalan, M.R. and Vellaipandian, S. (2013), *Big Data Framework for National e-Governance Plan*. Eleventh International Conference on ICT and Knowledge Engineering.
11. Rao, VVRM; Kumari, V. V and Silpa, N. (2015), "A Comprehensive Study on Potential Research Opportunities of Big Data Analytics To Leverage the Transformation in Various Key Domains", *International Journal of Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology*, Vol. 5(2), pp. 1-(18).
12. Twinomurizi, H. (2012), "The small group subtlety of using ICT for participatory governance. A South African Experience", *Government Information Quarterly*, doi:10.1016/j.giq.(2011).09.010.

ABOUT THE AUTHOR (S)

Kalyani Sahastrabuddhe is an Assistant Professor at Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

Ravindra Bavaskar is an Assistant Professor at Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

Shikhar Jha is a student at Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India.